

Fact Sheet B.

The National Empowerment Project (NEP): Cultural, Social, and Emotional Wellbeing (CSEWB) Program

This fact sheet describes a key community-led outcome of the National Empowerment Project: the Cultural, Social, and Emotional Wellbeing Program.

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Design

In 2012, the *National Empowerment Project (NEP)* consulted with 457 people in 11 communities across Australia to understand the challenges that are causing psychological distress and high rates of suicide in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities. *Aboriginal Participatory Action Research (PAR)* was used to ensure a culturally appropriate approach and that Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander voices were privileged.

During the NEP consultations the community reported clear protective and risk factors and the importance of Indigenous governance; that 'community knows best'. Aboriginal community members in the consultations recommended that a program be developed that was community-owned, strengths-based, and flexible (able to work with existing community resources and programs), and culturally-responsive (based on holistic ideas of health).

For Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples, healing is holistic, relational and collective. Healing involves several dimensions of wellbeing, as well as a consideration of the historical, political, social, and cultural determinants of health. This holistic view of health and healing is illustrated by the SEWB model.

The SEWB model was developed by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander psychologists in 2013 and, along with the NEP recommendations, formed the foundation of the CSEWB program (see Fact Sheet A and diagram to right). The SEWB model was also endorsed by the communities involved in the NEP consultations. During this process, community stated that culture is a significant factor and as a result the SEWB model was adapted to overtly include culture in the title and hence the term CSEWB was adopted.

The NEP principles also guide the CSEWB program. These include 1) social justice and human rights, 2) community ownership, 3) resilience and strengths focus, 4) respect for local knowledge, 5) build empowerment and partnerships, and 6) community capacity building.

Consistent with these protocols, the CSEWB program uses APAR approaches and strictly adheres to core principles of self-determination and empowerment, including community consultation, co-design, and facilitating local leadership and increasing community capacity.

SEWB Diagram adapted from Gee et al., (2014)

Aims and Purpose

The CSEWB program aims to strengthen the social, emotional and cultural wellbeing of individuals, families, and communities. By empowering communities to exert greater control over their CSEWB, the program takes a strengths-based, community development, and cultural approach to suicide prevention.

The CSEWB program assists participants and communities to build resilience, belonging, and strengthening cultural identity by identifying factors that impact negatively on CSEWB, and strengthening protective factors of CSEWB. Truth-telling, and connections to Country, spirituality, and cultural identity are built into every aspect of the program.

A decolonial approach that privileges Aboriginal ways of knowing, being, and doing is used to expand understandings of mental health and promote a narrative of strength and resistance. Central to this approach is a relational view of self and an understanding of culture as central to healing.

Delivery and Program

The program is delivered to up to 20 individual participants in an intensive 12 day program.

The CSEWB program is adaptable and acknowledges the diversity of Aboriginal peoples and community needs. The first step in implementing the CSEWB program is extensive community consultation to ensure community governance, engagement, and readiness.

A community reference group is established to advise how existing local services can be utilised within the program and how to best address community needs. Community engagement and endorsement are maintained at all stages of the program.

Program schedule:

- 1 Self:**
Introduction and storying
- 2 Self:**
CSEWB framework and colonial history
- 3 Self:**
Individual wellbeing and developing confidence
- 4 Self & Family:**
Stress management and interpersonal skills
- 5 Self & Family:**
Importance of family and Elders
- 6 Self & Family:**
Communication and building relationships
- 7 Parenting:**
Strengths of family 1 – intergenerational trauma
- 8 Parenting:**
Strengths of family 2 – child development
- 9 Community:**
Local and national histories and cultures
- 10 Community:**
Our future and self-determination
- 11 Community:**
Leadership and reciprocity
- 12 Review & Celebration**

“ I have the desire to have a life! I haven't wanted one for almost all of my 65 years. My mantra has always been: I don't belong, I feel like a square peg in a round hole. Well, for the first time I fit in! I belong! ”

“the key to the (program) success is that it comes from Aboriginal people, for Aboriginal people, and is delivered by Aboriginal people...”

Evaluation & Outcomes

1. Queensland

The program was initially delivered in two Queensland communities: Kuranda and Cherbourg. The 2017 evaluation report identified that the CSEWB program contributed to healing among families, strengthening role models for future generations, and reaffirming cultural identity in the participants and their communities.

NEP CSEWB Program Coordinator (QLD) Glenis Grogan stated: *“the key to the (program) success is that it comes from Aboriginal people, for Aboriginal people, and is delivered by Aboriginal people... When you really know who you are, you are able to become stronger in yourself. You can be a proud Aboriginal person. It’s not about us doing it to them. It’s about their own self-realisation – their responsibility, their family, their community – and what they can do to change it.”*

“It taught me that yes, we have culture and our culture is very strong and still alive and lives within us, we just have to believe in ourselves. I have become stronger, wiser, speaking out and more positive.”

2. Western Australia

The program is also delivered in Western Australia by Langford Aboriginal Association in three communities: Langford, Kwinana and Balga (Perth metropolitan regions). The NEP evaluation report reaffirmed the importance of culturally safe programs that acknowledge historical and social determinants of health at both local and national levels. The program evaluation provided strong evidence for the importance of relational and holistic models of health for the healing and empowerment of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples.

Program participants shared some of their stories of change:

“I have the desire to have a life! I haven’t wanted one for almost all of my 65 years. My mantra has always been: I don’t belong, I feel like a square peg in a round hole. Well, for the first time I fit in! I belong!”

“It taught me that yes, we have culture and our culture is very strong and still alive and lives within us, we just have to believe in ourselves. I have become stronger, wiser, speaking out and more positive.”

The CSEWB program has been recognised by communities across Australia and internationally, yet long-term commitment from government is needed to support and evaluate the delivery of these programs.

To find out more about the program or how to implement it in your community go to:

nationalempowermentproject.org.au
or timhwb.org.au/videos-photos

Transforming Indigenous
Mental Health and Wellbeing
www.TIMHWB.org.au

References

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